

CLINICAL AND IMMUNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DESTRUCTIVE CHOLECYSTITIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14796216>

Abstract. *Destructive cholecystitis is characterized by significant immunological changes that play a key role in the pathogenesis of the disease. In patients with this diagnosis, elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α) are observed, indicating a pronounced systemic inflammatory response.*

Changes in blood cell composition, including a decreased CD4⁺/CD8⁺ T-lymphocyte ratio and an increased number of NK cells, indicate an imbalance in immune regulation. Additionally, patients exhibit pronounced oxidative stress, characterized by a decrease in superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity.

These changes highlight the importance of understanding the immunological mechanisms in destructive cholecystitis, which may contribute to the development of more effective treatment strategies aimed at modulating the immune response and reducing inflammation.

Keywords: *immune regulations, SOD, pro-inflammatory cytokines, destructive cholecystitis.*

Relevance. Destructive cholecystitis is a severe inflammatory disease of the gallbladder, characterized by rapid progression and a high risk of complications such as peritonitis and sepsis [1]. Given the increased frequency of the disease and the significant number of severe cases, studying the pathogenesis becomes especially relevant [3]. Immunological changes play a key role in the development and progression of destructive cholecystitis, influencing the severity of the inflammatory process and the outcome of the disease [7].

Understanding the mechanisms of immune system activation, including the role of cytokines, complement, and cellular components of immunity, is crucial for the development of new diagnostic approaches [8]. In-depth study of immunological changes in destructive cholecystitis may lead to the development of targeted treatment methods aimed at modulating the inflammatory response, which could reduce the number of complications and improve the prognosis for patients [6]. Thus, the study of immunological aspects of destructive cholecystitis is an integral part of modern medicine and holds significant scientific and practical value [5].

From the perspective of current knowledge, the local inflammation developing during bacterial infection, systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS), sepsis, severe sepsis, and multiple organ failure are distinct links in the same chain of the body's response to the inflammatory process [4].

Changes in the ratio of T-lymphocyte subpopulations may indicate an imbalance in the regulation of the immune response, which could contribute to chronic inflammation and further tissue damage. Oxidative stress plays an important role in the pathogenesis of the disease, exacerbating cell and tissue damage [2].

Objective: It lies in the detailed study of immunological changes associated with destructive cholecystitis, and the development of new approaches to its diagnosis and therapy.

Materials and Methods. The study included 32 patients (18 men – 56% and 14 women – 44%) aged 40 to 65 years, with a mean age of 52.0 ± 1.22 years, who were diagnosed with destructive cholecystitis and hospitalized in the surgical department of the 7th City Clinical Hospital between 2023 and 2024. Inclusion criteria were the presence of a typical clinical picture of acute cholecystitis, confirmed by ultrasound (US) and computed tomography (CT) imaging.

Patients with concomitant systemic diseases, mental disorders, oncological diseases, and acute bacterial or viral infections were excluded from the study, as these factors could potentially affect the immunological parameters.

Immunological studies in the examined patients were conducted in several stages. The first stage involved determining the standard immunogram in peripheral blood, where the parameters of the cellular and humoral components of immunity, as well as cytokine synthesis, were assessed. Blood samples were collected from patients on the day of their admission to the hospital, before surgical intervention.

The control group consisted of 20 healthy volunteers (11 men and 9 women), matched for age and sex with the main group. Participants in the control group had no chronic diseases and had not taken any medications that could affect the immune system in the past 3 months.

The level of superoxide dismutase (SOD) was determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) using the Human Reader HS analyzer (Germany) and the ELISA-SOD test system (Cytokin LLC, St. Petersburg, Russia).

Descriptive statistics methods were used for data analysis: point estimates of the mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) were determined.

Results and Discussion. Changes in the blood cell composition included an increase in the number of neutrophils ($72.3 \pm 5.8\%$ vs. $55.4 \pm 4.7\%$, $p < 0.01$) and a decrease in the level of lymphocytes ($14.8 \pm 3.2\%$ vs. $30.1 \pm 3.5\%$, $p < 0.01$), indicating activation of the innate immune response. At the same time, there was a decrease in the number of CD4+ T-lymphocytes ($32.5 \pm 4.1\%$ vs. $45.7 \pm 4.8\%$, $p < 0.01$) and an increase in CD8+ T-lymphocytes ($25.3 \pm 3.7\%$ vs. $18.2 \pm 2.9\%$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a shift in the adaptive immune response (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Relative values of cellular immunity indicators in the examined patients

Activation of the complement system was observed, as reflected by an increase in the level of the C3 component (1.56 ± 0.2 g/L vs. 0.92 ± 0.15 g/L in healthy controls, $p < 0.01$) and the C4 component (0.48 ± 0.06 g/L vs. 0.26 ± 0.04 g/L, $p < 0.01$), indicating activation of both the classical and alternative complement pathways.

Patients with destructive cholecystitis exhibited a significant increase in the levels of IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-8, and TNF- α compared to the control group ($p < 0.01$). These changes indicate a pronounced systemic inflammatory response.

The obtained data confirm the presence of significant immunological changes in destructive cholecystitis. Patients showed a marked increase in the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including IL-1 β (35.2 ± 5.1 pg/ml vs. 7.8 ± 2.3 pg/ml in the control group, $p < 0.01$), IL-6 (12.5 ± 1.2 pg/ml vs. 4.7 ± 0.5 pg/ml, $p < 0.01$), IL-8 (70.3 ± 4.6 pg/ml vs. 15.6 ± 1.3 pg/ml, $p < 0.01$), and TNF- α (68.4 ± 7.9 pg/ml vs. 12.3 ± 3.1 pg/ml, $p < 0.01$). These data indicate a pronounced activation of the inflammatory response. (Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Comparison of Inflammatory Cytokine Levels Between the Control Group and the Main Group

Correction of oxidative stress in destructive cholecystitis reduces the process of destructive changes and is accompanied by the normalization of antioxidant status both at the systemic and local levels.

Our research showed that the most significant correlations between the studied cytokines and superoxide dismutase (SOD) in wound fluid were observed in the pairs IL-1 β /SOD and IL-4/SOD. Correlation analysis revealed a strong negative correlation between the levels of IL-1 β and SOD activity ($r = -0.68$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a decrease in antioxidant system activity as the inflammatory response increases. The level of IL-1 β in the wound fluid of patients was 28.7 ± 4.3 pg/ml, while SOD activity was reduced to 1.45 ± 0.22 U/ml compared to the control group (7.5 ± 1.6 pg/ml and 2.65 ± 0.35 U/ml, respectively, $p < 0.01$).

Similarly, the correlation between IL-4 levels and SOD activity was positive, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.61$ ($p < 0.01$), indicating the potential of IL-4 in stimulating antioxidant defense. The level of IL-4 in the wound fluid of patients was 15.6 ± 3.2 pg/ml, whereas its concentration in the control group was significantly lower (4.8 ± 1.1 pg/ml, $p < 0.01$). (Fig.3).

Fig.3. Cytokine and SOD Levels in the Control Group Compared to Patients

The most clinically significant finding was the increase in IL-6 levels, which showed a direct correlation with the severity of the patients' condition ($r = 0.72$, $p < 0.01$), confirming its key role in the pathogenesis of destructive cholecystitis and its potential as a biomarker for assessing the severity of the inflammatory process.

Thus, patients with systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) in acute calculous cholecystitis exhibited a cytokine imbalance, the severity of which depended on the number of criteria and the presence of sepsis. Surgical intervention in the context of cytokine imbalance and basic conservative therapy does not resolve it, indicating the need for adequate pharmacological correction.

Therefore, immunological changes in destructive cholecystitis include activation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, complement system, changes in lymphocyte subpopulations, and pronounced oxidative stress. These processes play a significant role in the disease's pathogenesis and can be used as targets for developing new diagnostic approaches.

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